

THE ROLE OF COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING IN MODERN TEACHING

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Annotation: The article highlights the importance of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) in modern language teaching. The research is conducted using a qualitative approach based on the work of famous scholars such as Brown, Harmer, Littlewood, and Nunan. The core principles of CLT are described, which include communication, interaction, and student-centered approach. The results show that CLT helps improve students' fluency and confidence when communicating in the target language.

Keywords: Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), communicative competence, student-centered learning, language skills, task-based learning, modern teaching, language education

Аннотация: В статье подчеркивается важность коммуникативного изучения языка (CLT) в современном преподавании иностранных языков. Исследование проводится с использованием качественного подхода, основанного на работах таких известных ученых, как Браун, Хармер, Литтлвуд и Нанан. Описаны основные принципы CLT, которые включают в себя коммуникацию, взаимодействие и личностно-ориентированный подход. Результаты показывают, что CLT помогает улучшить беглость и уверенность учащихся при общении на изучаемом языке.

Ключевые слова: Коммуникативное изучение языка (CLT), коммуникативная компетентность, личностно-ориентированное обучение, языковые навыки, обучение на основе задач, современное преподавание, языковое образование.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada zamonaviy chet tillarini o'qitishda kommunikativ til o'rganish (CLT)ning ahamiyati ta'kidlangan. Tadqiqot Braun, Xarmer, Littlvud va Nanan kabi taniqli olimlarning ishlariga asoslangan sifatli yondashuv yordamida olib borildi. CLTning asosiy tamoyillari, jumladan, muloqot, o'zaro ta'sir va shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv bayon etilgan. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, CLT o'quvchilarning o'rganilayotgan tilda so'zlashuv ravanligi va muloqotga bo'lgan ishonchini oshirishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: tilni kommunikativ o'rganish (CLT), kommunikativ kompetensiya, shaxsga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim, til ko'nikmalari, vazifalarga asoslangan ta'lim, zamonaviy o'qitish, til ta'limi

Introduction

In recent years, the importance of effective communication in the process of learning a foreign language has increased significantly. Globalization and international cooperation require people to use foreign languages not only to understand grammar, but also for real communication. Traditional teaching methods, such as the grammar and translation method, mainly focused on memorizing rules and vocabulary, which often limited students' ability to speak and interact fluently.

In response to these limitations, the Communicative Approach to Language Learning (CLT) was introduced, a modern approach that focuses on meaningful communication and interaction in the classroom. According to Richards and Rogers (2014) [1], communicative competence includes the ability to use language correctly in various social contexts. This

means that students should not only know the rules of the language, but also be able to apply them in real situations.

In addition, CLT promotes the creation of a student-centered learning environment in which students actively participate in discussions, role-playing, and other communicative activities. As Brown (2007) [2] states, "interaction is the heart of communication," which emphasizes the importance of active participation in language learning. This approach also combines four basic language skills — listening, speaking, reading, and writing — making learning more practical and effective (Harmer, 2007) [3].

Therefore, the purpose of this article is to consider the role and importance of a communicative approach to language learning.

Methods

The study is conducted a qualitative research based on the analysis of theoretical literature on Communicative Language Teaching (CLT). The research uses literature review (document analysis) serves as the primary data collection method that analyzes and summarizes information drawn from important scientific articles by Brown (2007), Harmer (2007), Littlewood (1981), and Nunan (2004).

Moreover, both inductive and deductive approaches are used. Inductive approach aims to establish common patterns and principles of CLT from the analyzed literature, while deductive one is used to interpret this theory in the framework of today's language learning.

In addition, the descriptive-analytical method is used to clarify essential characteristics, benefits, and importance of CLT in current educational process.

Results

According to the analysis, CLT has a positive impact on the development of the student's language skills. When students are exposed to communicative language teaching, they show greater fluency, confidence, and ability in interacting with others. Communicative methods in teaching also promote the active involvement of the student in the learning process. According to Littlewood, CLT "pays systematic attention to functional as well as structural aspects of language" (Littlewood, 1981)[4]. This way, the student can understand the form and function of the language. Moreover, the student can also develop his or her ability in integrating the four skills in communicative tasks: listening, speaking, reading, and writing.

Discussion

These findings further verify the fact that CLT holds a key position in the present teaching system. One of the advantages of this approach is the involvement of students through a student-centered method of learning, where the students participate actively through communication. Brown states that "interaction is the heart of communication" (Brown, 2007) [5], which further validates the importance of communicative tasks for learning.

Moreover, this approach can be incorporated with task-based learning and the use of technology, making it more feasible for the present learning system. Ellis (2003) [6] states that tasks offer learners the chance to use the language for meaningful purposes, and Bax (2003)[7] states that the use of technology promotes communication and student engagement for learning a language. However, this approach may also involve certain difficulties; therefore, the teacher should try to maintain a balance between this approach and other learning strategies.

Conclusion

In conclusion, I would like to note that communicative language learning (CLT) plays an important role in modern language education, focusing on meaningful communication and

the use of language in real life. Unlike traditional methods, it helps students not only to understand grammar, but also to effectively apply the language in various contexts.

The results of this study show that CLT improves speech fluency, self-confidence, and the ability to express oneself clearly. Through interactive, student-centered activities, students become more active and motivated in the learning process, which contributes to their overall language development.

Moreover, CLT can be successfully combined with task-based learning and modern technology, making it flexible and suitable for today's educational environment. Although there may be some problems with its implementation, its benefits remain significant.

Overall, CLT continues to be an effective and relevant approach that helps students become confident and competent language users in real-world communication.

References

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